

ISic1388

Greek dedication to Herakles

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

volcanic

Object

altar

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mendolito

Place of origin (modern)

Mendolito

Provenance

The stone was first reported by Torremuzza (1769, p. 269 cl. 18 nr. 39, on the basis of a report from Nicolaus Capretti), and repeated in CIG III, 5736. Orsi (1900) reports that it was for a long time walled into the Chiesa del SS. Cristo, before being removed by avv. Sanfilippo in whose collection at Adrano it was

when Orsi saw it. Orsi states that 'si sa che proviene dal Mendolito', but does not explain why he knows this. Libertini (1932, p. 12) attributes the stone to the site at Mendolito (along with , with reference to Orsi); Manganaro (1961, p. 132 n. 27) and Albanese (1991, p. 546 nr. 3) attribute the stone to contrada Polichello, south of Mendolito (again with reference to Orsi), but this appears to be the result of an overhasty reading of Orsi, who explicitly distinguishes Polichello from Mendolito, and attributes this stone to Mendolito.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Described by Orsi as a fragment of volcanic stone with a moulding around the top, intact above, below and on the right side, but broken on the left: the description is compatible with either a votive altar or a small base for a statue or other dedication. Orsi himself observed that the form of the stone with moulding along the upper edge is compatible either with the upper part of a stele/cippus, or as part of a small edifice.

Dimensions

Height 45 cm

Width 25 cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

single line of Greek letters, only partly preserved

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Orsi describes it as 'scritta a buone lettere', and his drawing shows slightly irregular broad square and simple letters: alpha with straight bar; rho with closed eye; kappa with long arms of equal length; epsilon with approximately equal bars.

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. [---]ϥ Ἡρακλεῖ

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1900

Orsi: .I HPAKΛEI

Translation (en)

[---] to Herakles

Commentary

Orsi reports a left leaning vertical hasta before the I at the left margin where the stone breaks off, which as he notes could either form a N with the vertical which he present as an I or else is part of a preceding letter, either A or Λ. Given that, as Orsi notes, this is probably the end of the name of the individual making the dedication to Herakles (which was already the intuition of Franz in CIG III, 5736), N seems simplest. Kaibel in IG XIV, 569 unnecessarily assumed that the stone was incomplete at the right end also and proposed alternative restorations of a name in the genitive such as Ἡρακλεῖ[ου]: Orsi was quite explicit, from autopsy, that (a) the stone is intact at the right end; and (b) that the surviving traces at the left were incompatible with ypsilon.

It is impossible to date this text, in the absence of further information, although it is most likely to belong to the Hellenistic period.

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Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0569 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Orsi, P. 1900. Frammenti epigrafici sicelioti. *Rivista di storia antica*. 5: 39-66. At 43 no.2

Albanese, R.M. 1991. Mendolito. In Nenci, G., Vallet, G.(eds.), *Bibliografia topografica della colonizzazione greca in Italia e nelle isole tirreniche*. Pisa. pp. 545-561. At 546 no.3

Castelli, Gabriele Lancillotto, principe di Torremuzza 1769. *Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio*. Panormus. At 269 cl.18 no.39

Castelli, Gabriello Lancellotto, Principe di Torremuzza 1784. *Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio prolegomenis et notis illustrata, et iterum cum emendationibus, & auctariis evulgata*. Palermo. At 287 cl.18 no.39

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 3.5736

Russo, S. P. 1911. *Illustrazione storico-archeologica di Adernò*. At 47

Manganaro, G. 1961. *Iscrizioni di Adrano*. *PdP*. 16: 126-135. At 132 n.27

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2. NI HPAKAEI

Drawing of P.Orsi, RSA 1900, p.43 no.2